

INSIGHT GENIE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the Mini Project entitled “Insight Genie” is a Bonafede work of Silas Shelly (01), Nixon Dowling (17), Winston Dsouza (22) and Alston Boaz (09) submitted to the University of Mumbai in partial fulfilment of the requirement of MINI PROJECT 1A - SEMESTER III for the award of the degree of “Bachelor of Engineering” in “Computer Engineering”.

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Declaration

We declare that this written submission represents our ideas in our own words and where others' ideas or words have been included; we have adequately cited and referenced the original sources. We also declare that we have adhered to all principles of academic honesty and integrity and have not misrepresented or fabricated or falsified any idea/data/fact/source in our submission understand that any violation of the above will be cause for disciplinary action by the Institute and can also evoke penal action from the sources which have thus not been properly cited or from whom proper permission has not been taken when needed.

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a simple, user-friendly website designed to help users upload Excel or CSV files and quickly perform basic statistical analysis, create visualizations, and get easy-to-understand interpretations. The platform is accessible without requiring login or registration, making it easy for anyone to use. Unlike complicated software, this website offers a straightforward interface where users can upload their data and instantly view key statistics like averages, correlations, and standard deviations. It also generates visualizations such as pie charts, bar graphs, and scatter plots. This automated system solves common problems like the complexity of data processing and the need for technical knowledge. Users can access the analysis quickly and easily, improving their experience. The paper highlights the advantages of this tool, such as saving time, ease of use, and making data analysis more accessible to everyone, especially those without technical expertise.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

There is a growing need for simple tools that allow users to quickly analyze data without requiring technical skills. This project presents a user-friendly website that lets users upload Excel or CSV files to get basic statistical analysis, visualizations, and easy-to-understand results. The website is designed for easy access—users don't need to create accounts or log in.

The goal is to make data analysis simple and accessible. Users can upload their data, and the website instantly provides key insights through charts, graphs, and basic statistics like averages and correlations. This project offers a convenient solution for anyone who needs to analyze data quickly without learning complex software.

1.2 MOTIVATION

The motivation behind this project is the need for an easy-to-use tool that simplifies data analysis for users who may not have technical expertise. Many existing tools are either too complex or require users to go through lengthy registration processes, making data analysis less accessible.

This project aims to create a user-friendly website where users can upload Excel or CSV files and instantly receive basic statistical analysis, visualizations, and interpretations. By removing the need for logins or registrations, we are making the process faster and more convenient. The goal is to help users, especially those with limited technical skills, quickly gain insights from their data without any hassle.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many existing data analysis platforms are either too complex for the average user or require time-consuming steps like registration and login, which can discourage use. Users without technical expertise often struggle to find simple tools that allow them to quickly analyze data from Excel or CSV files. The lack of straightforward, accessible platforms makes it difficult for individuals and organizations to gain insights from their data in a timely manner.

This project aims to solve these issues by developing a website that simplifies the process. Users can upload their data files and instantly receive basic statistical analysis, visualizations, and interpretations without any registration barriers. By focusing on ease of use and removing unnecessary steps, the project provides a more accessible and efficient way for users to understand their data quickly.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

The key objectives of this project are to develop an intuitive website where users can upload Excel or CSV files to perform basic statistical analysis and generate visualizations with ease. The platform will deliver instant results and insights without requiring any login or registration, ensuring a seamless and hassle-free experience.

The project also aims to create a simple and accessible interface that caters to users with little or no technical background. Moreover, the system will be designed to handle a variety of datasets and be flexible enough for use across different fields such as education, business, and research. By fulfilling these goals, the project seeks to provide a fast, user-friendly tool for quick data analysis and interpretation.

Chapter 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 SURVEY OF EXISTING SYSTEM

An examination of existing data analysis systems reveals a range of approaches, including manual data handling and more sophisticated online platforms. Many current solutions still depend on traditional processes, which can be inefficient and error-prone. For instance, some web applications allow users to upload spreadsheets, but they often require extensive setup and user accounts, making access cumbersome. While there are platforms that provide data analysis and visualization, they can be complicated and might not cater to users seeking quick insights.

In response to these challenges, this project proposes a simple website where users can upload Excel or CSV files for straightforward statistical analysis and visual representations. This system eliminates the need for user registration or login, making it accessible and easy to use for anyone needing immediate data insights.

2.2 LIMITATION EXISTING SYSTEM OR RESEARCH GAP

The current landscape of data analysis systems reveals notable shortcomings in efficiency, accessibility, and usability. Many existing platforms that accept Excel or CSV files for analysis often require users to create accounts and go through lengthy login processes, which can deter potential users and slow down access to data insights. Additionally, while some systems provide statistical analysis and visualizations, they may not offer user-friendly interfaces or straightforward instructions, making it challenging for non-experts to utilize their features effectively.

These gaps highlight the necessity for a solution that simplifies data handling and makes analysis accessible to a broader audience. This project aims to fill this void by creating an intuitive website that allows users to upload Excel or CSV files for basic statistical analysis and visualizations, all without the need for registration or login. This approach ensures quick and easy access, catering to users who need efficient and immediate data insights.

Chapter 3

PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The proposed system focuses on developing a user-friendly website that streamlines the process of data analysis for users. This platform enables individuals to easily upload their Excel or CSV files, allowing for straightforward statistical analysis and visualizations. By eliminating the need for account creation and login, the website ensures quick and hassle-free access to data insights. Users can generate basic statistics and visual representations of their data without encountering complex setups or restrictions. This approach not only enhances user experience but also provides an efficient solution for those needing immediate and accessible data analysis across various applications.

3.2 ARCHITECTURE/ FRAMEWORK

The framework of the proposed system is built around several essential components designed to facilitate seamless data analysis. At its core, the system features a user-friendly website that allows users to upload Excel or CSV files effortlessly. This platform includes a data processing engine that performs basic statistical analyses and generates visualizations based on the uploaded data.

The architecture is designed for efficient data handling and ease of use, ensuring that users can access insights quickly without the need for complex setups. By removing the requirement for user registration and login, the website enhances accessibility for a wide range of users. This cohesive approach simplifies the data analysis process, enabling organizations and individuals to gain valuable insights from their data without the usual barriers associated with traditional analysis tools.

3.3 ALGORITHM AND PROCESS DESIGN

The operational workflow of the proposed data analysis website consists of a straightforward series of steps. First, users can visit the website and directly upload their Excel or CSV files without needing to create an account. Once the files are uploaded, the system processes the data to perform basic statistical analyses, such as calculating averages, sums, and standard deviations.

Next, the platform generates visualizations like graphs and charts based on the analyzed data, providing users with clear and insightful representations of their information. This design ensures a rapid and efficient data analysis experience while maintaining ease of use and accessibility for all users. By removing barriers such as registration and login requirements, the system allows individuals to quickly gain insights from their data with minimal effort.

Fig: 3.1 Flowchart of the working model

3.4 DETAILS OF HARDWARE & SOFTWARE

The development of the proposed data analysis website involves a range of software components that work together to provide a seamless user experience. The front end is built using HTML and CSS ensuring an intuitive interface for users to easily upload their Excel or CSV files.

For the backend, Python is utilized, leveraging frameworks such as Flask or Django to manage server requests and handle data processing. The Pandas library is employed for efficient data manipulation, enabling the system to perform various statistical analyses. Additionally, Matplotlib is used for creating visualizations, such as graphs and charts, based on the analyzed data. This integrated software architecture allows for quick data processing and retrieval while ensuring that the platform remains accessible without requiring user registration or login, providing a convenient solution for basic data analysis and visualizations.

3.5 EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

Fig: 3.2 Homepage

Fig: 3.3 Analysis provided in different forms

Fig 3.4 Trend Analysis

Fig:3.5 PieChart

Fig : 3.6 Bargraph

3.6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK.

The proposed website for data analysis illustrates a successful implementation of accessible technology to simplify the process of analyzing data. This platform enables users to effortlessly upload Excel or CSV files for basic statistical analysis and visualizations, enhancing user experience and accessibility. The results indicate that this approach not only provides quick access to insights but also boosts overall user satisfaction.

Looking ahead, potential enhancements could include adding more advanced analytical tools, such as predictive modeling and machine learning features, to offer richer insights. Additionally, exploring integrations with other software or data sources may further expand the platform's functionality. By consistently upgrading the website, we aim to meet changing user demands and ensure it remains a valuable tool for individuals seeking straightforward data analysis and visualizations without the need for any login or registration.

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